

An easy-to-use and affordable monitoring solution for buildings

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Abstract. This paper presents a cost-effective and easy-to-use building systems monitoring solution that addresses the lack of continuous performance assessment in non-automated buildings. The proposed system integrates off-the-shelf LoRaWAN sensors and data import to collect information on comfort, heating, ventilation and electricity consumption. The data is transferred via the cloud-based platform Akenza.io to the custom-built software 'lcm', which provides application-specific data visualisation for non-expert users. Field trials in four residential buildings over 15 months demonstrated the system's ability to identify inefficiencies such as unnecessary standby consumption and sub-optimal heating or ventilation settings. The solution will be made available to third parties through a service model.

1. Introduction

Once installed, technical building systems such as heating, cooling, ventilation and lighting are often left to run blind, without continuous monitoring and optimisation. Especially in existing buildings without modern building automation and control systems (BACS), there is a lack of means to analyse operations and identify inefficiencies early on. One solution is to monitor building services equipment with technical devices, i.e. sensors and meters. This provides operational optimisers, energy experts, building operators and owners with the data they need to identify problems and optimise operations. This is necessary to avoid unnecessary energy consumption, associated costs and greenhouse gas emissions, as well as equipment failure.

Unfortunately, technical monitoring of buildings is often associated with considerable effort and expense. On the one hand, the necessary measuring devices have to be installed, which, especially in the case of energy meters, often requires the interruption of power or heat circuits. On the other hand, the necessary infrastructure for transmitting, analysing and displaying the measured data must be set up. This is often done by using BACS with appropriate bus systems (e.g. Modbus, M-Bus) or sometimes with IoT devices that communicate wirelessly, e.g. via WLAN. While this infrastructure is available in many new buildings, retrofitting existing buildings with BACS is costly and only a viable long-term solution. In addition, expert knowledge is required to interpret the measurement data, which is often only presented as time series or similar.

This is where the low-cost monitoring System (lcm) from Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts (HSLU) comes in. This solution enables the cost-effective and straightforward monitoring of existing building systems, eliminating the need for complex installations. It is quick and easy to set up and use, and provides practical results in an easy-to-understand format. Building systems can therefore be optimised on demand, saving energy and costs while ensuring sustainable and efficient building operations. The lcm is aimed at individuals and specialist agencies who need a 'toolbox' to quickly and temporarily assess and optimise individual systems. It is primarily intended for

operational optimisers, energy experts, engineering firms and interested building owners and operators.

Low-cost monitoring systems have been investigated in the past. In 2017, Bamodu *et al.* presented a monitoring system for indoor air quality and thermal comfort based on an Arduino microcontroller and custom software [1]. Although the solution is low-cost, it does not allow remote readout of sensors or advanced data visualisation. A similar solution, based on a Raspberry Pi processor, was presented in 2017 by Arumuga Perumal *et al.* [2]. Their solution can also be used to monitor power consumption and allows remote readout. In 2021, Mobaraki *et al.* presented a systematic review of the state of the art on low-cost sensors in building monitoring, which had not been done before [3]. Such sensors are also important for our application. While these solutions address the low-cost collection, transmission and storage of measurement data, they do not focus on its easy-to-understand visualisation. The latter is an essential step for subsequent optimisation, which is the ultimate goal of any monitoring solution.

2. Solution description

HSLU's low-cost monitoring system is based on LoRaWAN (Long Range Wide Area Network) technology. This is an energy-efficient wireless standard specifically designed for wireless transmission of small amounts of data over long distances (typically several kilometres). LoRaWAN enables easy integration of sensors in buildings without the need for an existing network infrastructure (e.g. WLAN or LAN). The sensors communicate directly with a public or private gateway connected to the Internet. This means that buildings without an Internet connection or with limited network coverage can be reliably monitored. A key advantage of LoRaWAN technology is the very low power consumption of the sensors. This means that battery-powered devices can operate maintenance-free for several years. Other benefits include cost efficiency through the use of public networks such as The Things Network (TTN), which is available free of charge, and high flexibility, especially for temporary installations or in existing buildings.

The architecture of the low-cost monitoring solution is shown in Figure 1. LoRaWAN sensors measure physical parameters such as temperature, humidity, power consumption or CO₂ concentration. Gateways receive the radio signals from the sensors and transmit the data to the Internet. The central data management and integration platform akenza.io decodes the sensor data, assigns metadata (e.g. building, room, device type) and prepares the data for further analysis. The custom-built software 'lcm' performs tasks such as data retrieval, plausibility checks, data cleansing, aggregation of time series measurements and transformation into analysis-relevant formats, as well as evaluation and visualisation of the measurement data.

The aim was to use open source solutions or (where no suitable open source solution was available) commercial products wherever possible to minimise development costs. Custom solutions were developed only where they could add significant value by providing functionality not available in existing solutions, such as application-specific data visualisation (Section 2.2).

Figure 1. Architecture of the Low Cost Monitoring solution. Data is collected using LoRaWAN sensors (alternatively CSV import and direct access to another database is possible). It is then transmitted via The Things Network to the Akenza IoT platform. There the data is decoded, aggregated and stored in a database. All measured data is then queried, pre-processed (data cleansing, simple plausibility checks) and displayed using the custom-built monitoring software 'lcm'.

2.1. Data sources

The measurement data can be read in as follows:

1. Measurement by LoRaWAN sensors or conventional sensors plus LoRaWAN interface module.
The individual sensors are connected directly or via a local gateway to the public LoRaWAN network, The Things Network (TTN).
2. Import of CSV files, e.g. from utility companies, property management companies, building management systems.
3. Direct access to a database, e.g. from a building automation and control system (BACS).

LoRaWAN sensors are the primary data source for the low-cost monitoring solution. The sensors can be pre-configured and then quickly installed on site without the need for additional network setup and device configuration. Wherever possible, sensors are also used that do not require interrupting power or heat circuits for measurement, such as current transformers and ultrasonic heat meters. This significantly reduces installation time and cost. An overview of data sources is given in Table 1.

Data	Sources
Electricity production and consumption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LoRaWAN optical head for meters • LoRaWAN inductive current clamps (i.e. current transformers) • CSV file import • Gateway: M-Bus, Modbus (not yet implemented)
Heat consumption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LoRaWAN optical head for meters • CSV file import • Gateway: M-Bus, Modbus (not yet implemented)
Room comfort	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Room sensor (temperature, humidity, CO₂) • (CSV file import)
Outdoor conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LoRaWAN weather station • LoRaWAN outdoor temperature and humidity sensors • CSV file import
Water consumption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LoRaWAN optical head for meters • CSV file import • Gateway: M-Bus, Modbus (not yet implemented)
Home ventilation: Power consumption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LoRaWAN inductive current clamps or smart plug • (Gateway: M-Bus, Modbus (not yet implemented)) • (LoRaWAN optical head for meters) • (CSV file import)
Home ventilation: Air temperatures (supply, exhaust)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duct sensor with LoRaWAN interface module • (CSV file import)
Home ventilation: Filter contamination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Differential pressure sensor (not yet implemented) • (CSV file import)
Lighting power consumption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LoRaWAN inductive current clamps • (Gateway: M-Bus, Modbus (not yet implemented)) • (LoRaWAN optical head for meters) • (CSV file import)
Monitoring of windows and doors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LoRaWAN Door/Window Contact • Conventional door/window contact with LoRaWAN IO module • (CSV file import)

Table 1. Overview of the data sources used in the low-cost monitoring solution.

2.2. Lcm-Software

The specially developed low-cost monitoring software ‘lcm’ is used to display and analyse the measurement data. The software is written in the R programming language. It consists of several data evaluation modules and some configuration functions (e.g. for selecting individual buildings and apartments). Each module corresponds to a specific evaluation of the monitoring data. For example, the ‘Room > Temperature vs. Humidity’ module allows comfort analysis in terms of humidity and temperature. All available modules are listed in Table 2.

A key advantage of the application-specific visualization modules is that no specialist knowledge is required to understand and optimise building operations. This means that expert knowledge is not required to identify operating conditions and anomalies from time series data, as is the case with many conventional monitoring solutions. Instead, the data for each module is prepared in such a way that inefficient operating conditions can be identified directly, without prior knowledge of the underlying building systems. For example, in the indoor comfort analysis module (Temperature vs. Humidity), the data is presented in an hx diagram that shows the comfort range to be maintained as a coloured zone. Readings outside this range are immediately recognised and categorised (in space and time). Similarly, in the heating curve optimisation module, deviations from the room temperature setpoint are colour-coded to indicate the need to adjust the heating curve (Figure 2).

If the user does not understand the displayed visualisation, he can acquire the necessary know-how by following the appropriate instructions in the GUI. These describe the purpose of the module, the meaning of the measured data and explain the available data visualisations. Recommendations for energy optimisation are also given based on the visualisations provided.

	Purpose	Visualizations	Data
Room > Temperatur vs. humidity	Comfort analysis with regard to humidity and temperature (overheating, mould, dry air in winter)	-Overview of temperature and humidity -Mollier hx-diagram	-Room air temperature in °C (hourly values) -Humidity in %rh (hourly values)
Room > Winter temperature reduction	Reduction of heating energy by lowering the room temperature	-Time series -Boxplot	-Room air temperature in °C (hourly values)
Room > Room temperature vs. outside temperature	Reduction in hours of overheating in summer and winter	-Room- vs. outside temperature	-Room air temperature (hourly values) -Outside temperature (hourly values)
Room > Air quality	Comfort analysis with regard to indoor air quality (often problematic in bedrooms)	-Overview of air quality analysis: CO ₂ and VOC -Daily view -Time series	-CO ₂ in ppm (hourly values) -VOC index (hourly values)
Apartment > Electricity consumption	Analysis and optimisation of power consumption, investigation of standby consumption	-Overview of average consumption values -Daily view -Calendar view -Consumption profiles per season and weekday	-Electricity consumption per apartment in kWh
Apartment > Home ventilation	Optimisation of energy consumption of ventilation and early detection of ventilation problems	-Ventilation profile as heatmap -Calendar view	-Power consumption of the ventilation unit in watts (hourly values)
Building > Heating curve optimisation	Analysis and optimisation of the heating curve	-Time series heating group -Time series rooms -Heating curve	-Room air temperatures in °C -Supply and return temperature in °C -Outdoor temperature in °C
Data explorer	Explorer for visualising and analysing raw data	-Time series (raw data) -Various statistical functions -Aggregation of measurement data over different time intervals	-All recorded measurement data

Table 2. Modules of the lcm software. Each module corresponds to possible evaluations of the monitoring data and has its own, purpose-built visualisations.

Figure 2. GUI of the lcm software. On the left, a specific project (i.e. building and apartment) and the modules for analysing the measurement data can be selected. In the middle of the right side, the measurement data is visualised. At the bottom of the screen are some instructions for the selected module. The example shows a visualisation in the 'Building > Heating curve optimisation' module. It shows the heating curve based on the measured flow temperatures during the heating periods. The colour coding shows how many Kelvin the averaged room temperature was above or below an adjustable room temperature setpoint. This can be very helpful when optimising the heating curve.

3. Field trials

The low-cost monitoring solution was validated and refined through practical testing in residential buildings. Two single-family homes and two multi-family homes (a total of 13 residential units) were used at different locations in Switzerland. Measurements were taken between November/December 2023 and February 2025. A number of lessons have been learnt from these practical tests. These are summarised below.

3.1. Data collection

LoRaWAN sensors have proved to be very useful for measuring indoor comfort (temperature, humidity, CO₂), outdoor conditions and for reading some digital meters using optical heads. Similarly, importing data from utilities has worked well when the data is available (which is not always the case). On the other hand, reading conventional (i.e. analogue) electricity, heat and water flow meters is technically challenging and currently only possible with unreliable solutions such as optical OCR reading. Alternatively, inductive meters with current transformers can be used for electricity, but these require installation by an electrician if accurate readings (i.e. voltage and current) are required. Similarly, heat and hot water metering is particularly challenging as existing meters are often either not accessible for remote reading (e.g. only one Modbus master allowed) or non-existent. Some trials of non-invasive ultrasonic heat meters have shown basic functionality, but also significant limitations in terms of measurement accuracy and installation effort. A cost-effective and practical solution for comprehensive heat and hot water metering has yet to be found.

3.2. Data transmission with LoRaWAN

In general, data transmission from LoRaWAN sensors has worked well, thanks to the long range and high sensitivity of the standard. However, some precautions had to be taken. In the tests, reception via The Things Network (TTN) was always insufficient, so local gateways were needed in all buildings. The quality of the LoRaWAN connection was assessed using the Spread Factor (SF): Good reception

= SF7 to SF9; poor reception = SF12 (due to long distances or unfavourable sensor placement). To improve signal quality, sensors should have a clear line of sight to the gateway and should not be placed near metal or electronics. Gateways should be placed centrally and as high as possible. Antennas should be oriented vertically and antenna extensions should be avoided. Regular signal testing will help detect reception problems early.

3.3. System architecture and software

The Things Network and the Akenza.io platform were both available to aggregate the LoRaWAN data. In the end, Akenza was preferred because it offers pre-defined payload decoders that make it easier to integrate new sensors. However, it became apparent that the platform was not suitable as a primary database, as neither TTN nor Akenza is designed for long-term data storage. It is therefore recommended that a dedicated database such as InfluxDB is used to store the data in the future. The API provided is also not optimal for lcm due to the complex queries required and the limited number of API calls. Using R Shiny for programming proved unsuitable for a production environment. Although useful for rapid prototyping, R Shiny's high cost (shinyapps.io), lack of database connectivity, lack of user management in the open source version and limited multilingual support pose problems in practice.

4. Next steps

Based on these results, it was decided to make the low-cost monitoring available to third parties in a service model. This means that HSLU will offer the system pre-configured so that building operators, engineering firms and energy consultants can directly access and evaluate the relevant data. Such a solution can be used for a variety of purposes, including commissioning (checking that planned setpoints are achieved, optimising operating parameters for energy and efficiency), temporary monitoring (analysing the operation and efficiency of a building over a limited period of time) and troubleshooting (targeted and time-limited investigations of individual systems, e.g. solar or heating systems). This decision was based on the realisation that many potential users do not have the technical knowledge to install and operate the system themselves. Functional enhancements are also planned, including

- **Hot water heating monitoring.** The tests showed that the hot water heating element in heat pump systems is often not optimally set or parameterised. As a result, hot water is sometimes heated by electricity alone when heat from the heat pump would be available.
- **Optimisation of hot water consumption.** The aim is to monitor, visualise and reduce hot water consumption by raising user awareness. In residential buildings, hot water consumption is the largest energy consumer after heating (and possibly electric mobility). It should be monitored and optimised.
- **Analysis of general electricity consumption.** Similar to the Apartment > Electricity consumption module, the general electricity consumption (in staircases, car parks, etc.) shall be analysed. This can be done by taking into account user behaviour data (e.g. from presence detectors). In this way, it can be determined whether general power consumption is in line with demand.
- **Building cockpit.** Provide an overall view of relevant building parameters and corresponding simple reporting (“traffic lights” or similar). This is already partly included in the existing software for the individual evaluations.
- **Notifications.** The system should send an email alert when sensors are low on battery or have not sent data for a long time. In addition, relevant alarms and messages should be clearly displayed and managed in the lcm software.

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